

Collection of specimens for reproductive studies

Photo-Identification guide

Authors: Maria Rakka, Marina Carreiro-Silva, Cova Orejas

Scleractinia

Hard calcareous skeleton
Six-fold symmetry

Lophelia pertusa

Robust reef-forming species

Madrepora oculata

Typical Zig-zag formation

Collection of specimens for reproductive studies
Photo-Identification guide

Scleractinia

Hard calcareous skeleton
Six-fold symmetry

Dendrophyllia cornigera

Yellow colour

Long, strong corallites (polyp cases)

Desmophyllum dianthus

Mostly solitary but can form
small aggregations

Big, oval shaped polyps

Collection of specimens for reproductive studies
Photo-Identification guide

Octocorallia

Polyps: eight-fold symmetry
covered with sclerites

Callogorgia verticillata

Bushy colonies
White or pink

Irregular branching

Upward polyps
Facing each other

Polyps covered with many rigid sclerites;
extremely fragile to handling!

Paracalyptophora josephinae

Bushy colonies
White
Symmetrical form

Dichotomous
branching
Downward polyps
Arranged in rows

Collection of specimens for reproductive studies
Photo-Identification guide

Octocorallia

Polyps: eight-fold symmetry
covered with sclerites

Viminella flagellum

Acanthogorgia armata

A. armata and *A. hirsuta* can only be distinguished by differences in polyp density. In case of doubt, identify as *Acanthogorgia* sp.

Collection of specimens for reproductive studies
Photo-Identification guide

Octocorallia

Polyps: eight-fold symmetry
covered with sclerites

Dentomuricea meteor

Tree-like shape
Yellow colour

Gavin Newman ©Greenpeace

ARQDAÇO-ImagDOP

Acanella arbuscula

ATLAS-MEDWAVES

Bush-like shape
Redish colours

Bamboo-like nodes

ATLAS-MEDWAVES

Disclaimer: This guide solely aims at helping with at field sampling of coral specimens. For formal specimen identification, it is highly recommended to use taxonomical guides

Collection of specimens for reproductive studies
Photo-Identification guide

Antipatharia

Black rigid skeleton with small spines
Polyps: six-fold symmetry; soft; totally uncovered; do not retract

Leiopathes sp.

Bush-like shape
Orange/red colour

Soft polyps
Often covered with
mucus

Antipathella wollastoni

Bush-like shape
White/pink/brown
colour

Soft, small polyps
Often covered with
mucus

Endemic in Macaronesia!

Disclaimer: This guide solely aims at helping with at field sampling of coral specimens. For formal specimen identification, it is highly recommended to use taxonomical guides.

Acknowledgments: Images were taken with the following financial support: H2020 ATLAS project (grant agreement No 678760), MEDWAVES cruise (ATLAS, Spanish Ministry of Economy, Industry and Competitivity (Grant COC-DI-2015-12), ARQDAÇO monitoring programme (Regional Government of the Azores), MIDAS (Grant Agreement No 603418), Greenpeace.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 678760 (ATLAS). This output reflects only the author's view and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.